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Transcript

Hi, thank you so much for taking your time to participate in this interview. My name is Anna Makarudze, and I'm pursuing a master's towards software engineering at the Pleasure Institute of Technology, and I'm conducting research to investigate the perspectives of developers with regards to vulnerable dependencies they use within their project, especially with the rise of supply chain attacks are burning through open source dependencies. I'm focusing on five web frameworks, Python, Django, which is based on Python, then Next.js, Springboot, Laravel, and Ruby on Rail. Participation in this research is entirely voluntary and begin withdraw from the interview at any time. We will not retain any personal data or identifiable information and your name, role, e-mail address, and any identifiable details will not be published or shared with anyone.

You can skip any questions you are not comfortable answering and your responses will remain anonymous and not be linked to you. The interview is being recorded and will be kept for the admission of the study to allow the supervisor to verify the authenticity of the recorded data after which the recording will be.

Speaker 2

Okay, so I want to confirm if I'm possible enough.

Speaker 1

Sorry.

Speaker 2

Hello.

Speaker 1

Hello.

Speaker 2

Okay, so I'm a software developer. And then heavily I work on fronting with a couple of them based in this space with experience with different technologies, especially with students that I want to talk on actually. That's basically what I mean. And for my, what's it called, academic background. So I'm a graduate of University of Marine and I studied mathematics and also currently a student of Niva University where I purchase my, where I'm pursuing my master in technology as well.

Speaker 1

Good to know. And how many years of experience do you have as a software developer?

Speaker 2

Okay, let me say I have about seven years of experience, but when it comes to working experience, I have about four years of experience.

Speaker 1

And how long have you been using Next.js?

Speaker 2

That should be three years.

Speaker 1

So do you do you use Next.js to work on commercial projects or do you also contribute to open source projects based on next year?

Speaker 2

I think that was once that I made use of Next.js contributing to open source projects and that should be last year.

Speaker 1

And outside loop JavaScript in Next.js, do you use Other ecosystems, maybe Python, Java, PHP, Ruby.

Speaker 2

Okay. Okay. I can see earlier my stage as a developer, I was on my microsoft PHP, but in the recent years, so I worked heavily on Python and then JavaScript framework, not the Varina, JavaScript or Python for their frameworks and libraries. for Python like Django, Flux, and FastAPI. So I do that as well. And for JavaScript, Next, React, and Svelte.

Speaker 1

All right. My research is mainly focused on security. So I want to understand how are security issues handled within the projects that you work on? Suppose there is a security vulnerability bit.

Speaker 2

Okay, talking with your experience, I have some right. So I think around last year, I cannot remember the month specifically, but it was around Q3, Q4. So there was a particular launch of attack, I don't know, group, or there was a particular launch of attack that affects a lot of dependencies on them. So over a couple of months, we are receiving a lot of mail from GitHub. GitHub is actually doing well in that case. So whereby they keep notifying us about these vulnerabilities and the dependencies they keep attacking in our project. So and then that's how we've been dealing with this for, you know, especially this use of AI stuff, like, I mean, these new adventure of this AI is actually costing our project. I don't want to say problem, but, you know, everything has their own pros and cons, right? so and then that's one of the cons of this AI so it's kind of bringing a lot of security leakage like especially the ways developer use the AI recently and also apart from that the way this AI access our code and then try to all those attackers really use it to attack our code and then access our information so that is what I can say for that for now all right.

Speaker 1

And my next question will have been, how aware are you of the dangers that vulnerable dependents present to your project?

Speaker 2

OK. I think one of the things that make it supports is actually the GitHub Dependabot, right? So because that's one of the vulnerabilities in our code, apart from using some node package, a node command that the NPM audit to actually check for if there is any vulnerability in our code, especially next particularly. So apart from that one, one of the things that we are using is also the GitHub Dependabot. They don't work in that aspect. So whereby they keep notifying us whenever there's an attack based on, there's something calls and call them CVEs that's like the kind of critical how critical are this attack so they try to list this attacking in how critical in hierarchy right you know okay this is actually too risky high risky low risky some of that and is that we tend to attend to them based on how risky they can be so that's how we get the information yeah okay and.

Speaker 1

Are you aware of supply chain attacks and their effects on projects?

Speaker 2

Sure.

Speaker 1

What's what influences a decision to update vulnerable dependencies is within your project?

Speaker 2

OK. OK, let me just say this as I want to maybe some of the restaurants for instance now. You know, this attack, supplying attack that we're talking about, it's just like the rest, okay? In the case of a restaurant, right? They need to get ingredients to actually, there was a call, prepare their food or whatever. And then they're not doing, we developer, we are just like the cooks or the owner of the restaurants. We don't, some of the time, we don't even know what is going on, we just purchase or we just get supply, we just get ingredients for our food from suppliers, which is like, we just get dependencies from these people. We don't even know if there's an attack there. And, you know, we trust them. That is why we are actually getting the ingredients for them. But when we now start preparing these ingredients, make it a food and start additional to customers, when they start eating it, of them, it's not as if we are doing bad, but, you know, it is just like the way the things actually come. So, but in some cases, we will actually attempt to be supply attack is, okay, there are some things that we cannot actually do, cannot actually survive. And that is the fact that there are some supply attack in our dependence that we are able yet to find solutions to them. And we are not even, we are not even because in this case, it is the people managing those dependence, you know, each dependence they have like community or some type of people that do manage them, right? I think for instance, I think that was late last month.

That was March 30. Yeah, that was about three days ago. So I received a mail from GitHub dependents about one project I'm working on. So the project is like, it's just like I kind of maintain the project. But one of the information I got was that there was actually some supplies attacked in some of my dependent sites. So when I, when I check through these dependents, I notice some of them, they are kind of updates. They're kind of like, they're kind of the mortality for me to use so that I can actually be out of this supply attack while some of them have yet to actually find the solutions to it. Take for instance, there's this particular dependent I make use of that as GUILL. So the function is actually to You know, there's this concept of what you write is what you see, right? Especially when you're dealing with content management system, right?

So like posting the content and everything. So in this case, I make use of, I was initially going to use React, a React quid or something, but it doesn't actually supply me what I need, so I need to go for that quid. So, and I received the mail about four days ago that the quid I'm currently using, there are kind of supply attack, So how do I go about that?

That's like the kind of question we do ask ourselves and especially that there is no update from these OSS, I mean, all these FOSS and all these free open source system. Exactly. So in that case now, I just have to keep watching over until I get a new update from them and I can now update my system except that I want to move out from the dependency. But seeing there's not happening, I just have to keep watching. And also I have to be very sure this supply attack is not actually affecting my users, like users of the application. So that's it.

Speaker 1

Okay. And how do you check the maintenance of the dependencies you use in your projects? For example, how do I check the maintenance of the project dependence you are using in our projects uh given that uh you know open source uh packages they are maintainers sometimes just abandon their projects and you are using them how do you check to see that the dependence you are using are still being maintained and in the event of the vulnerability uh the maintenance will be able to fix them okay um.

Speaker 2

We actually test using NPM audit, like to check if there's been vulnerable in our dependence. NPM audit. And then like, ah, when we now test to get find a kind of, then there are two ways to it. It can be more than that. For my own end, I make use of two ways. It's either I check if there's an obvious, but just like the way you mentioned, I about, it might have been just abandoned dependence. How do I go about it? So I try to find alternative for it, especially I have to be very sure before, if I kind of, if I didn't want to go for alternative, I have to be very sure the supply attack in that dependence is not actually affecting anything in my project, right?

Like it won't affect anything in my project. And then also if I see that it is going to affect, then I have to switch for the alternative, like similar dependence that you see in kind of and was it for function I want to use that dependence for?

Speaker 1

And uh normally how long does it take to update the vulnerable dependencies within your project in the event that there's uh a plague maybe from GitHub?

Speaker 2

Okay when you want to update sometimes it's very easy in the sense that especially when it comes to this next JS of stuff so it's very easy when you update it's update automatic like it takes minutes. I let me use seconds. It takes minutes just within less than 5 min, less than 3 min. You are done updating. But sometimes where, if if the dependency actually take a larger percentage of your application. If, for instance, now you are using reactor dump doesn't for your linking everything. So and There's a, maybe there's a kind of supplier type in this reactor domain, you need to update it, right? You know, you might have been using this reactor like at a larger percentage system, but I used to update it. In some case, those updates, they form with some stuff that they are not actually compatible with some of the existing dependency that we are working with, right?

So in that case, the first issue, especially this happens a lot when we are working with Flutter, right? Because I write Flutter as well for mobile application. So it happens a lot with Flutter. That is when just tends to see that, okay, you update the dependency and the dependency you are using is not actually compatible with other dependencies. So in that case, it takes time to update. But in other way round, if you don't, if you don't have yourself in that kind of situation, then it takes minutes, just as a three minutes, five minutes, you are done updating whatever dependency wants to update.

Speaker 1

And how do you handle dependencies that are no longer maintained? Would you fog them and take over the maintenance yourself or we'll just switch to either alternative?

Speaker 2

Okay, let me just use this. It's not a dependency, just like a package for running our, for installing our application. So for instance, at least last year, PRA, that's where the application was kind of downgraded. That is, you can no longer install your application using your PRA because of like, I think they've embedded the project. So they were not, there's no, the people are no longer kind of managing it. So they dump it.

And then in that case, you know, what I did from my own end is like some of the project that I feel like they are kind of the projects that need like, what's it called, proper maintenance, right? You know, some projects when you're done with them, that's why some units to keep maintenance.

So if I don't set in that kind of situation, then you have to update to the latest one so that you can meet up with what is going on. But in the project thereby, it is actually like, what I

did, what I did was like I moved some of these projects from craft to vites, like using vites instead of craft.

So, in that kind of situation, as well, in this dependency store, my final set is a situation whereby I feel like this project is something you need to keep maintaining, like maybe the projects I'm working on, you have to keep maintaining so that it can meet up with the current ecosystem is you have to find alternative, right?

You have to find alternative so that you can, and especially when these projects, you know, just like the way I mentioned earlier, the compatibility of this dependence on banks can be kind of frustrating. So you have to find a way to go for alternative that has maintenance, right? Whereby you won't be having issue in the long run of, okay, this independence is not compatible with this kind of dependency.

Speaker 2

That is how I agree about this.

Speaker 1

And what influences you pick a dependence within your projects? Do you just take it because it does what you, it just offers the functionality that you need or do you have some criteria of determining whether to include that dependence or not?

Speaker 2

Okay. There are different routes. The first route is, you know, if you're working with some projects, they are going to give you TRP. That's a technical requirement for that project, right? So in that case, this means your research on which dependency, which technology to use is going to get mini tech, right?

So whereas there are some cases you have to recommend to them that, okay, you have to use this based on this, you have to use it. And in some cases, like let me even say in most cases whereby we don't receive it for a project.

So what we do is just like make use of dependency based on the functionality or based on the text of that project. Right. So that's like what we do.

Speaker 1

Okay. Do you consider its popularity or how? How long it has been in existence or you just pick it because offers the functionality you need?

Speaker 2

Over the time, this has always been kind of discussion in the sense that when we want to work on a project, do we choose dependency based on popularity, right? Let me take for instance now. People prefer, some people, they prefer using React and DOM instead of Tankstar, right, for their routing. So, and why they use this aircraft atom is because it's kind of popular, but Tankstar is kind of easy to manage. Like it works something similar in a way how, what's it called? Next app routing work, like app routing, how it's working next year side.

So, so like it can, it's a discussion that I've always been going on. Do we choose technology or dependency based on popularity? or based on usage. For my own case, I feel like I need to choose based on, not based on popularity, based on what I want to use it for. But in some case, I have to consider that, okay, what's the, what's the lifespan of this project?

This is something that has to do it long time, right? So in that case, I have to consider the one that has a better ecosystem like that has that always have people to review and always update it other than maybe popularity or stuff.

Because, you know, at the long run, say, for instance, after a few months, they term the, what's it called, the dependency, right? So it means you have to be looking for something else, or you have to have your handy writing another, like trying to update dependency to another authority.

So like that, from my own end, I feel that's the way it should be, right? So we shouldn't kind of choose based on popularity, should be based on future and also what is the, okay, what's actually the lifespan of the dependency?

Like are people actually maintaining it? And even if they are maintaining, what is actually like time, what is the time range of how they release updates? Exactly.

Because you know, in this case, in this era now we are having like a lot of security attack, a lot of them. So which implies there's need for consult. So I didn't for was a constant maintenance in this. And then so equity and what's it called people managing it also like, that's what we consider when choosing independency to use.

Speaker 1

Hmm. Oh, okay, thank you. Thank you for that. So what tools and okay before I ask that do you have a security team within your projects that handle security issues or it's up to the developer?

Speaker 2

Actually uh with with on my experience especially with this startup right they I I think they do they always neglect security like expertise in their projects when they're, I don't know the way, like they consider, they consider security personnel as a post store, not actually a brand, right?

So it is only when they start receiving a card in their projects that is when they now feel like they don't want to consider a security expert in their project or with experience, more than average of companies or more than average of projects, whenever they are working on it,

They feel like the developers to be the ones to like subconsciously that like what they think because if not, they should have actually included a security expert in that project. But they feel like developers should actually work on the security aspect as well so that attacker cannot come into it.

But it is when they start receiving attack, that is when they feel like they need to include security person. And sometimes, sometimes, right, the kind of the concept of the project or the kind of requirement of that project also will give a definition that, okay, should they actually include the security as part?

You know, for instance, that if they're building, let's say, for instance, they're building a CMS, that's an ordinary content management system, right? They might fly there's only for them to include a security aspect in that project.

But you know, you are working with a project that has to maybe a fintech application now or a fintech project or something similar. So they might need to consider it as carefully. So that's how it is like. That's how that's my experience.

Speaker 1

And what tools and practices are you using to mitigate supply chain attacks in your project.

Speaker 2

Okay. I make use of two things, right? For my own case, I make use of NPM audit to check for vulnerable NPM audit. So in some cases, I want to make it further. I can write some CI/CD that's in continuous integration and continuous developments to check vulnerables in my project and then always alert me before even the project goes to production stage, right?

But in a very large extent, I depend more on the GitHub Dependabot and GitHub dependence because, you know, in some cases, it is even after you might have to launch the project, that is when the supplier path comes into the dependence, right?

So that's when I consider going, I mean, that's why I kind of use both tools, right?using NPM to check for vulnerables in the dependent before even going to live or before even pushing to production. And also stick to GitHub Dependabot. GitHub Dependabot is actually like something included in GitHub already.

But you can also make it a kind of like, yeah, you can also make it automatically that it creates a pull request to feed vulnerable dependencies in your code. And that one, you have to set it in that security, in the settings of that particular area code, in the security tab.

So like something like you have to, that's like the way I used to do it, like I make use of NPM audit and also rely on dependable security updates from GitHub, right?

Speaker 1

And then you, I don't know. uh if any of your projects uh been exposed to supply chain attacks.

Speaker 2

Yes I was about to say that I don't know if it is in I don't know if it is permitted I would like to share one of the okay I'm trying to check my mail so one of the attack I received isn't.

Speaker 1

You can forward me maybe um If you think it's something that you can share, you can always send to me details over e-mail.

Speaker 2

Okay, no problem with that. I'm going to forward it to you.

Speaker 1

Thank you. And what challenges do you face when addressing vulnerable dependencies in your project?

Speaker 2

Okay, the challenge I face, some of them, it's, you know, some of these projects, right, when you work on them, Especially it's like a contract project, contract based project. After you are finished, after you are done working on the project, you don't have access to the for the game.

But in some case, you still receive some updates on vulnerabilities. In that case, as a developer, sometimes that that's conscious. You are going to be feeling that conscious

that this particular project is a simple some attack, though it might not be affecting the project itself. Right? So that's on. That's like one of the challenge.

One of the challenges we face as well is also trying to find authenticity that best suit a particular dependency that receives a supply attack. And that dependency is no longer managed or there is no update for authenticity.

Sometimes when they kind of receive supply attack, they tries to work on fixing it and then create a latest version or an updated version for it. But sometimes there's an attack in the dependency, but there is no update yet.

And also to find alternative that actually best suits that feature you are looking for, right?So just like the example I cited earlier, like I was about using React skill and there are some features I need in that I was able, what you pack is what you see, functionality that wasn't implemented, but I could not get some React is how to use boots for like

And in that case now, there's an attack currently, and there's no update here. That's at 31st of March. That was about two days ago. Now, if I want to go for alternative, to get alternative that actually has that kind of functionality I'm using for is an headache. So that's one of the challenging things, like trying to get a better suit and was it for alternative for the particular dependence that I received the supply attack?

Speaker 1

And what what makes it easy or what helps you to address vulnerable dependence within your projects? You have talked about the challenges and what factors make it easy to for you to address the vulnerable dependence in the project.

Speaker 2

Okay, just like I mentioned earlier, DCM was a call. It's all Dependabot right? What makes it easy, right? Because it's not even like you're trying to. You might have worked on hundreds of projects like, do you not say that you want to be taking for dependency every single day.

But for this, for this Github Dependabot, right? It gives a proper update like a kind of updated version of what is going on in your project.

And with that it's very easy to manage. I give kudos to Github on that aspect, actually. So it's very, very easy to manage. So since you are receiving constant like time, a time reach constant, and information about what's going on in your application.

I think about 50 15 days or something. So it's kind of easy to manage that way.

Speaker 1

And do you have any recommendations for other developers on how they can manage open source dependencies to mitigate supply chain attacks in their project?

Speaker 2

Okay. I have a couple of advice. One of the advice is always to check for vulnerable before even making use of the, what's it called, dependence, like making use of an NPM audit to check if there's an, if there's a vulnerable in the dependence, that's a first thing.

And also they should care more about people managing the particular dependency. Like, is this something like, you know, if you check some dependency, right, the timeframe for the the update is always like, maybe sometimes can be a year like the last update there is.

Maybe it was like about a year ago. 2 years ago, sometimes like that. You know, in that case it means there is no proper management in that in that dependent like.

So it should be at most it should be maybe 6 months or something, especially this era of the AI that we're talking about.

So because I mean, I used to, I used to discuss this with my colleagues that this AI of the store, as not that it is actually like making our work easier, but it is creating more work for cybersecurity personnel in the.

Speaker 1

Okay. Thank you.

Speaker 2

There was a discussion yesterday in one of my, I was, we were discussing with one of my team yesterday and in about it, this AI was talking, they were like, we're now in the era of fast, I cannot remember the way they phrased the word, but it was like something like, we're now in the era of fast production and lesser, that we care very less about security, the security leakage in our product or in our project, but we are now like in a fast era of production.

Like we fast, we ship production in hours in days, right? And we don't even consider, what's it called, the security of the stuff. So one of the address I can give is also like, we should make use of like, we should be very, very careful about how we make use of AI. Yeah, those are the, I think that's about three of them now.

So the first one, always check for vulnerables. And second, make sure you are kind of very aware of the people managing the dependency as well. How constant do they update? Do

they give updates or do they even give information or clear information about the dependent?

And also in that case, I think that's where the popularity comes in, right? You know, sometimes it has to do like, okay, this one is very popular about this one. And what makes them popular is because of people managing them. Like they have a lot of community, like a lot of people in their community.

And it does make use of this AI stuff too. right to manage and also to deal with our product.

Speaker 1

All right, thank you so much for your time. I think that's all for me. I really appreciate you taking your time to participate in this interview.

Speaker 2

Thank you very much.

Speaker 1

All right, I'll stop right now.

Speaker 2

Okay, bye.